

Transition metal complexes of tetraazamacrocycles : Synthetic and spectral aspects

Anil Bansal and R. V. Singh*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, India

Fax : 91-141-515367

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Nitrogen bonded square-planar complexes of the type $[M(\text{mac}_1)]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[M(\text{mac}_2)]\text{Cl}_2$, [where $M = \text{Pd}^{\text{II}}$ and Pt^{II}] have been synthesized. The template condensation of adipic acid with primary diamines, i.e. 1,2-diaminoethane and 1,3-diaminopropane in the presence of metal salts results in the formation of macrocyclic complexes. The complexes are monomeric and 1 : 2 electrolytic in nature.

The synthesis of polyamide macrocycles and their coordination chemistry are of particular interest in view of two potential donor atoms, i.e. amide nitrogen and amide oxygen¹. However, in most of the polyamide macrocyclic complexes, amide nitrogen is engaged in coordination and not the oxygen². There is a considerable interest in the metal ion chemistry of polyazamacrocycles, stimulated by their unusual thermodynamic stability and kinetic inertness. They are responsible for the stabilization of rare oxidation states of transition metal ions³. Recently, dramatic progress in the chemistry of tetraazamacrocyclic complexes in particular has been made since these structural units are involved in a variety of catalytic, biochemical and industrial process⁴. Macrocyclic Schiff base complexes of transition metals have been shown to be useful for their applications to organic syntheses and clarification of the reactions in living processes. Recently, a large number of reports has appeared concerning the chemistry of specifically functionalized macrocycles, where the complex contains reactive groups on the periphery of a macrocyclic ring, which has been termed as 'ligand super structure'⁵.

The design and synthesis of binuclear macrocyclic transition metal complexes where the metal ions are in close proximity remain an important objective as potential catalysts, models for a number of metalloproteins and in investigations concerning the mutual influence of the two metal centres on the electronic, magnetic and electrochemical properties of such closely spaced paramagnetic centres⁶. The macrocyclic donor fixes the metal ions and this determines, within the limits of the macrocycles flexibility, the internuclear distance.

Herein we report the synthesis and characterization of some new palladium(II) and platinum(II) complexes of

twenty- and twentytwo-membered tetraazamacrocycles from the reactions of primary diamines with dicarboxylic acid.

Results and Discussion

The metal ion controlled reaction of metal salts with primary diamines and dicarboxylic acid resulted in the formation of a new series of tetraazamacrocyclic complexes $[M(\text{mac}_1)]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[M(\text{mac}_2)]\text{Cl}_2$ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1.

The analytical data (Table 1) suggest that the reaction is carried out in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratio. The resulting complexes

are coloured solids having high melting points. The monomeric nature of these complexes is confirmed by molecular weight determination. The molar conductance of 10^{-3} M solutions of the compounds in anhydrous DMF ($215\text{--}230 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate their behaviour as 1 : 2 electrolytes⁷. These complexes are freely soluble in DMF and DMSO but slightly soluble in common organic solvents.

A square-planar environment of the ligand around the metal ion has been proposed on the basis of infrared, electronic and ^1H NMR spectral data.

IR spectra : In the IR spectra of the macrocyclic complexes, a single peak is observed at $3405\text{--}3448 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to OH of iminol group. The second medium intensity band at $1588\text{--}1615 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned⁸ to the imine C=N stretching vibration whose position is consistent with that of a coordinated C=N group and which indicates the formation of the azomethine group during the condensation. This is also an evidence for the formation of the macrocyclic framework. The appearance of a new band at $412\text{--}445 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (M–N) suggests that the imine nitrogen is coordinated to the metal atom. The absence of a band attributed to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ vibrations indicates that the iminol oxygen is not coordinating.

Electronic spectra : In the electronic spectra three *d-d* spin-allowed transitions are expected in these complexes corresponding to the transitions from the three lower lying *d*-levels to the empty $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals. The ground state is $^1A_{1g}$ and the excited states corresponding to the above transitions are $^1A_{2g}$, $^1B_{1g}$ and 1E_g in order of increasing energy. Three *d-d* bands observed at $582\text{--}590$, $505\text{--}522$ and $394\text{--}405 \text{ nm}$ in the present metal complexes may be assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{2g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_g$ transitions⁹, respectively. The electronic spectra of these complexes indicate a square-planar geometry around the metal(II) ion and the values obtained correspond to those reported earlier¹⁰.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes

Compd./ Emp. formula	Colour M.p., °C	Yield %	Metal % : Found/(Calcd.)	Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
[Pd(mac ₁)]Cl ₂	Cream	52	20.13	230
C ₁₆ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pd	247		(20.54)	
[Pd(mac ₂)]Cl ₂	Yellow	56	19.85	221
C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pd	229		(19.49)	
[Pt(mac ₁)]Cl ₂	Grey	60	31.77	215
C ₁₆ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	268d		(32.19)	
[Pt(mac ₂)]Cl ₂	Brown	49	30.38	226
C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂ Pt	236		(30.77)	

^1H NMR spectra : In the ^1H NMR spectra of the complexes, a broad signal observed at δ 8.66–8.85 may be assigned to the iminol proton. [M(mac₁)]Cl₂ and [M(mac₂)]Cl₂ giving a singlet and a multiplet at δ 3.02–3.06 and 2.91–2.96, respectively, correspond¹¹ to

methylene protons adjacent to the nitrogen atoms. A multiplet at δ 1.91–1.97 for [M(mac₂)]Cl₂ is assigned to the middle methylene protons (C–CH₂–C) of 1,3-diaminopropane moiety. A multiplet at δ 3.10–3.20 may be ascribed to methylene protons of the dicarboxylic acid moiety (=C–(CH₂)₂–C=) which are adjacent to nitrogen atom. The above results, along with the absence of any signal corresponding to free primary amino protons, strongly suggest formation of the proposed macrocyclic skeleton.

Experimental

All the solvents used were of high purity and distilled before use. Palladium(II) chloride, platinum(II) chloride, 1,2-diaminoethane and 1,3-diaminopropane (E. Merck) and adipic acid (Fluka) were used as such. Moisture was excluded using CaCl₂ guard tubes.

(2,7,12,17-Tetrahydroxo-1,8,11,18-tetraazacyclododeca-1,7,11,17-tetraene)metal(II) chloride, [M(mac₁)]Cl₂ : A mixture of the metal salt PdCl₂/PtCl₂ (0.005 mol) 1,2-diaminoethane (0.01 mol) in methanol (50 ml) and a methanolic solution (25 ml) of adipic acid (0.01 mol) was stirred for 11 h and then kept for 8 h at room temperature. The resulting coloured compounds were washed with methanol, dried, crystallized from benzene and dried again under reduced pressure.

(2,7,13,18-Tetrahydroxo-1,8,12,19-tetraazacyclododeca-1,7,12,18-tetraene)metal(II) chloride, [M(mac₂)]Cl₂ : The procedure was the same as described above, but using 1,3-diaminopropane instead of 1,2-diaminoethane. For the crystallization of the complex it was dissolved in hot benzene (25 ml) and set aside overnight at room temperature. The resulting crystals were dried under reduced pressure. Electrical conductivities (10^{-3} M solutions in dry DMF) were obtained on a Systronic 305 conductivity bridge. Molecular weights were determined by the Rast camphor method¹². M.p.s. were determined in capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Nicolet Magna FTIR-550 spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Jeol FX 90Q spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Palladium and platinum were estimated gravimetrically¹³. N and Cl were determined by Kjeldahl's and Volhard's methods, respectively¹⁴. C and H analyses were performed at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, India.

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